

Integrated germplasm improvement — irrigated

Mukti-CTH1, a rice with cold tolerance and blast resistance for winter and ratoon cropping in Karnataka, India

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More than 700 genotypes from local germplasm and entries of the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery were screened at the UAS research stations, Bangalore. The work to develop cold-tolerant and blast-resistant varieties was done in collaboration with IRRRI and the Indian Council of Agricultural Research.

Under natural conditions, the cultivars CTH1, CTH3, and CTH4 were identified as tolerant of cold and resistant to blast, besides being nonlodging. During a 1986 winter trial at Bangalore, CTH1 (B2983b-SR-85-3-2-4 from Indonesia, derived from Sirendah Merah/IR2153-159-1-4) was outstanding. It has 90-100 cm plant height and medium slender grain type. It has been in multilocation trials and in farm trials in Sep and Oct plantings in the southern districts of Karnataka. As IET 11220, it was in All India Coordinated Trial (AICT) for hills. Its blast score at Ponnampet was 3, compared with 7 for Intan.

Under winter conditions, CTH1 yielded 1.3-4.3 t/ha, against 0.0-2.5 t/ha of the best local or currently grown winter variety. It ranked first in 10 plantings in Bangalore and was the only variety to produce some yield (3.2 t/ha) when planted in Oct at Nagenahalli. It ranked second in two of five locations in the hill region in the AICT. CTH1 matures 125-130 d from sowing. Its cooking quality is good and the grain is reportedly very good for puffed rice. Its kernel is red and falls under mid-fine category. Its excellent ratooning ability is yet another potential that can be exploited. ■

Divya (WGL 44645), a newly released rice variety for gall midge (GM) endemic areas

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Divya (WGL 44645), derived from WGL 23022/Surekha, is a short-duration (125-130 d) rice variety, suitable for year-round cultivation. It has the gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason resistance from Eswarakora in WGL 23022 (CR44/W 12708) and from Siam 29 in Surekha (IR8/Siam 29). With its high resistance (zero infestation at 8 of 10 sites), Divya is suitable for GM (biotype I) endemic areas.

Divya is semidwarf with compact plant type, photoperiod-insensitivity, fertilizer-responsiveness, and grain yield potential

of 6.0 t/ha. The kernel is long slender (length:breadth = 4.21) with no abdominal white.

In 1981-86 trials, Divya gave consistently high yields (see table). During 1988 wet season, it ranked first at the Directorate of Rice Research (DRR), Hyderabad Centre; third at Agricultural Research Institute, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad; and ninth among 64 entries in the preliminary variety trial 2 of DRR. During 1989 wet season, Divya ranked first at Pondicherry, fourth at Pattambi, and fifth at Mandya and at 8 other sites among 15 entries, and was superior to Vikas and Ratna in the uniform variety trial 2 of DRR.

It gave higher grain yield than checks in multilocation trials (1983, 1984) and minikit trials (1985-88) at different sites in Andhra Pradesh. It is popular among farmers of the Northern Telangana Zone. ■

Performance of Divya (WGL 44645) in yield trials at ARS, Warangal, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)						Mean
	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	
Divya (WGL 44645)	4.8	4.5	4.1	4.3	4.0	4.2	4.2
Pothana	3.2	-	-	-	-	-	3.2
Telia Hamsa	-	2.7	-	-	-	-	2.7
Vijay Mahsuri	-	-	3.4	3.2	2.3	3.8	3.2
LSD (0.05)	0.7	0.4	0.3	0.5	0.4	0.2	
% increase over check	29.3	52.5	21.4	33.6	73.9	10.7	

Chaite 4, a short-duration, high-yielding rice variety for double-cropped areas in Nepal

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Nearly 90% of the total rice area of Nepal is located in the tropical to subtropical region; two crops of rice are grown with assured irrigation, followed by one winter crop. The first rice crop, known as *Chaite dhan*, is

planted in Mar in the southern plain area (the Tarai).

Farmers in the inner Tarai and river basin areas (altitude 250-1,000 m) in the mid-hills start seeding the first week of Feb. The early season rice crop (Feb/Mar to Jun/Jul) is followed by the main season rice crop (Jun/Jul to Oct/Nov). Intermediate-tall, traditional type rice variety CH45 (China 45) is the most widely planted. Short-duration rice varieties are needed for the *Chaite dhan* crop, to allow timely planting of main season rice.